

THE MOST EFFECTIVE WAYS TO DEVELOP THE STUDENTS' CONVERSATIONAL ABILITIES IN TEACHING FOREIGN LANGUAGES

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Annotation: Nowadays everything is changeful, particularly, in teaching the English language. In fact, there is a great difference of methods of educating foreign languages to young generations namely pupils. Each teaching method is mainly based on a particular vision of comprehension the language or the learning process, frequently using specific techniques and materials used in a set sequence. Language teachers who deeply study and use various methods of teaching English are those who take care of their own value to self, to pupils, to family, to society and to a larger community of the world.

Key words: community, language teaching learning process, frequently, techniques and materials, fluently, various methods, particular vision, experienceю

Annotatsiya: Hozirgi kunda xususan ingliz tilini o'rgatishda ko'p usullari o'zgarimoqda. Darhaqiqat, yosh avlodga, ya'ni o'quvchilarga chet tillarini o'rgatish usullarida katta farq bor. Har bir o'qitish usuli asosan tilni yoki o'quv jarayonini tushunishning ma'lum bir tasavvuriga asoslanadi, ko'pincha ma'lum bir ketma-ketlikda qo'llaniladigan maxsus texnika va materiallardan foydalanadi.

Kalit so'zlar: jamoa, til o'rgatish o'rganish jarayoni, tez-tez, texnika va materiallar, ravon, turli usullar, alohida qarash, tajriba

Аннотация: в настоящее время все меняется, в частности, в обучении английскому языку. На самом деле существует большая разница в методах обучения иностранным языкам молодых поколений, а именно школьников. Каждый метод обучения в основном основан на определенном видении понимания языка или процесса обучения, часто с использованием определенных методов и материалов, используемых в определенной последовательности. Учителя иностранных языков, которые глубоко изучают и используют различные методы обучения английскому языку, заботятся о своей ценности для себя, учеников, семьи, общества и всего мира.

Ключевые слова: сообщество, процесс обучения языку, часто, приемы и материалы, бегло, различные методы, особое видение, опыт.

It is universally accepted that language teaching of students is the most complicated process. Language gives definition to our memories and, by translating experiences into symbols, converts the immediacy of craving or abhorrence, or hatred or love, into fixed principles of feeling and conduct. Diverse ways of educating English can be both demanding and challenging for teachers along with pupils, they can also be tremendously stimulating and rewarding. Having English as a second language opens up many work opportunities no matter what ethnicity, colour or background a person comes from. Being able to speak English allows parents to teach their own children to speak the language from an early age, making it that much easier for the children to get to grips with the grammar, vocabulary and idiosyncrasies of the language. This is one of the important reasons why it is so important to be able to speak English because it means your children will benefit too. Having English as a second language often means a person can command more in the way of salary. Being able to speak English will demonstrate a level of intelligence to others, especially if spoken fluently without hesitation or the need to search for words. The fact you may have an accent really does not matter whatsoever as long as your pronunciation is good enough to be understood. In fact, accents are thought of as quite charming by most native speaking English people. Aldous Huxley (1958) once wrote, "Language has made possible man's progress from animality to civilization". In doing so, he effectively summarized the importance of language in humans' lives. It is through language that we are civilized. One could argue that nothing is more important to the human species than that. But Huxley wasn't done there; he continued by explaining the value of language: Language, in other words, is how we think. It's how we process information and remember. It's our operating system. Vygotsky (1962) suggested that thinking develops into words in a number of phases, moving from imaging to inner speech to inner speaking to speech. Tracing this idea backward, speech – talk – is the representation of thinking. As such, it seems reasonable to suggest that classrooms should be filled with talk, given that we want them filled with thinking!

Let's spend a few minutes analyzing this classroom exchange. First, it's not unlike many of the whole-class interactions we've seen, especially in a classroom where the students are obviously having a difficult time with the content. One student at a time is talking while the others listen or ignore the class. Second, the teacher is clearly using a lot of academic language, which is great. We know that

teachers themselves have to use academic discourse if their students are ever going to have a chance to learn. Third, the balance of talk in this classroom is heavily weighted toward the teacher. If we count the number of words used, minus the student names, the teacher used 190 words, whereas the students used 11. This means that 94 percent of the words used in the classroom during this five-minute segment were spoken by the teacher. In addition, if we analyze the types of words used, half of the words spoken by the students were not academic in nature. That's not so great. Students need more time to talk, and this structure of asking them to do so one at a time will not significantly change the balance of talk in the classroom. As you reflect on this excerpt from the classroom, consider whether you think that the students will ever become proficient in using the language. Our experience suggests that these students will fail to develop academic language and discourse simply because they aren't provided opportunities to use words. They are hearing words but are not using them.

We are reminded of Bakhtin's (1981) realization: "The world in language is half someone else's. It becomes 'one's own' only when the speaker populates it with his own intention, his own accent, when he appropriates the word, adapting it to his own semantic and expressive intention". As we analyze why many students are not learning what we are teaching, we must evaluate our own practice for evidence of student talk throughout the day. Oral language is the foundation of literacy, and as such, it requires focused attention in planning. Altering the ratio of teacher to student talk doesn't just happen. Rather, it occurs through both believing in the importance of student talk and planning with a clear purpose and expectations. But before we discuss how to plan lessons that integrate purposeful academic talk, reading, and writing, we must be clear on our own understanding of exactly what academic oral discourse is. We turn our attention now to an analysis of the elements of discourse in the classroom. Language permits its users to pay attention to things, persons and events, even when the things and persons are absent and the events are not taking place. English, being the language that's accepted throughout the world, is the one language that's worth mastering. English is used in so many main industries including the realms of films and computers. It's the one world language that opens doors to those who can speak it fluently. It may be challenging to learn at first, but with all the modern technologies which includes having access to online English courses and word game software, life has been made that much easier. Once you

appreciate all the reasons why it is so important to be able to speak English, should motivate you to do so to the best of your abilities.

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